

Intra-Prostatic Injection of Epinephrine During Transurethral Resection Of Prostate Reduces Blood Loss And Need For Blood Transfusions; A Randomized Controlled Trial

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 28, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: April 29, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Transurethral resection of Prostate, Epinephrine, Blood transfusion, Hemoglobin, Hematocrit.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6506083</p>	<p>Objective: <i>To assess the role of Intraprostatic injection of epinephrine intra-operatively in patients undergoing TURP in decreasing blood loss and need of subsequent blood transfusions. Design: A double-blind randomized controlled trial. Place and Duration of Study: The Kidney Centre Postgraduate Training Institute, Karachi, from March till August 2020. Methodology: A total of 40 patients were chosen at random and divided into two groups of equal size. One group got an intra-prostatic injection of epinephrine, whereas, the other received a standard saline injection. Both groups were evaluated in terms of prostate volume (ml), resected tissue (gms), surgical resection time (minutes), pre and post-operative Hemoglobin (HB) and Hematocrit (HCT) levels. Intra-operative blood loss was then quantified using the last two variables. Transfusion requirement in both groups was also recorded.</i></p> <p>Results: Mean +Age of patients in Group A and Group B was 66.30 + 9.24years and 65.65 + 7.43years, respectively, with no significant difference between both groups ($p=0.808$). Median and IQR Prostatic volume in Group A and Group B was 68.0, 15, and 64.0,21 which suggests there was no statistically significant difference between the two groups ($p=0.372$). Mean + S.D Loss of HB of patients in Group A and Group B was 1.15 + 0.42 and 1.87 + 1.04 respectively, with significant difference between both groups ($p=0.007$). Mean + S.D of post-op HCT of patients in Group A and Group B was 3.16 + 1.50 and 4.81 + 2.79 revealing a significant difference between the two groups ($p=0.026$). No patients in Group A needed blood transfusions, whereas 6 patients in Group B had blood transfusions, indicating a statistical distinction between the two groups ($p=0.001$).</p> <p>Conclusion: <i>The use of intra-prostatic injection of epinephrine leads to reduced blood loss and subsequently reduced operative time, irrigation fluid usage, and blood transfusion during TURP. It also allows greater amount of prostatic tissue to be resected.</i></p>

Introduction

Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is a frequent scenario in senior men that results in a mix of storage/irritative and voiding/obstructive symptoms. It leads to a persistent decrease in detrusor effectiveness in emptying of the urinary bladder and aggravates lower urinary tract symptoms.¹ Older men are far more likely to develop BPH; 50% do so in their 50s and 60s, whilst in their 70s, 90% of men have symptoms attributable to a hyperplastic prostate. As a result, this illness is both a community and health concern, with significant financial implications for both the patients and the society in terms of healthcare costs.^{2,3}

As per the European Association of Urology, patients with moderate - to - severe symptoms should consider medical therapy, such as alpha-1-adrenoceptor antagonists, as a first-line treatment. The medications help to relieve bladder-related symptoms while also improving urine flow (Qmax). Patients with huge prostate glands (more than 80 gms), who are not responding to medicinal therapy, may be considered for operative intervention. Among the surgical options, Transurethral resection of prostate (TURP), has established itself as a standard procedure for treating patients with LUTS caused by obstructive benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH). Other options include Transurethral incision of the prostate (TUIP), Transurethral vaporization of the prostate (TUVVP), Transurethral vaporization-resection of the prostate (TUVRP), Transurethral microwave thermotherapy (TUMT), Transurethral needle ablation (TUNA), Interstitial laser coagulation of the prostate (ILC), and Holmium Laser Enucleation of the Prostate (HoLEP).⁴

Surgical options, specifically TURP, can prevent problems such as urinary discomfort, urinary tract infections, and urosepsis, result in shorter hospital stays and lower expenses, as well as improved overall quality of life.⁵

However, 15–20% of TURP patients may encounter major complications such as hematuria, bladder neck stricture, urinary incontinence, retrograde or anejaculation, and transurethral resection syndrome. 10–15 % of patients may also require a repeat operation within 10 years.⁵ However, blood loss continues to be one of the most common complications. In fact, according to a published case series, blood transfusions were required in roughly 2.9 percent of cases of TURP.^{6,7}

Various methods and drugs have been used peri-operatively to minimize this blood loss. One example is use of intra-prostatic injection of epinephrine, before tissue resection, which may influence a reduction in peri-operative blood loss during TURP.

For this purpose, we are conducting this study to add to the data that intraprostatic epinephrine injection during TURP can improve institutional practices for the benefit of patients undergoing such intervention and, therefore, changes in the future protocols/guidelines might be shaped and innovated accordingly.

METHODOLOGY

From March 2020 to August 2020, a randomized controlled trial was conducted in The Kidney Centre Postgraduate Training Institute, Karachi, for a period of 6 months. It was an experimental, double-blind trial. Before beginning this study, an ethical clearance from the board was sought (Ref: 74-URO-012020).

All symptomatic males with BPH requiring TURP were included in this study. Exclusion criteria included patients with abnormally high blood pressures, ischemic heart disease, blood dyscrasia, urinary lithiasis, those using anticoagulant medications, or having undergone any urological surgical intervention in the previous three months.

Two equal groups of 20 patients were assigned at random, labeled Group A, the Case group and Group B, the control group. The analyst was a senior registrar who was in charge of randomly assigning groups to the patients. The surgeries were performed by different surgeons that were unaware of the drug being administered, as were the patients (double-blind). Group A received an intra-prostatic epinephrine injection (200mcg diluted in 20ml normal saline), while Group B received a 0.9% normal saline injection (20 ml). Both groups were compared in terms of prostate volume (mL), resected tissue (gms), resection time (minutes), pre-op Hemoglobin (Hb) and Hematocrit (HCT), post-op Hemoglobin (Hb) and Hematocrit (HCT), as well as the need for blood transfusion. All procedures were carried out under General Anesthesia.

Before the procedure, the prostatic volume (ml), and pre-operative Hemoglobin and Hematocrit levels were obtained. Cystoscopy was carried out with 21 Fr rigid cystoscopy sheath with 30° optical lens for examination of the whole urinary tract especially the urethra, prostate, and urinary bladder. 10ml of the designated solution (epinephrine in Group A; normal saline in Group B) was injected in the median lobe while 5ml was given in both lateral lobes of Prostate with a 20G metal needle (making a total infusion of 20 ml). Five minutes after the injection, TURP procedure was carried out with 26 Fr resectoscope sheath. Prostatic chips were cut with a monopolar electrocautery loop. Continuous cardiac monitoring was done to note any rhythmic changes due to epinephrine. Time of prostate resection was noted in minutes and chips of resected tissue were measured in grams.

Post-operatively, patient's Hemoglobin (HB) and Hematocrit (HCT) levels were also collected. Blood transfusion requirement was assessed in both groups as well.

Open EPI sample size calculator was used. Each group had a sample size of 20 patients and mean blood loss, by comparing pre and post-op Hb and HCT levels, was estimated in Group-A and Group-B at a 95% confidence level and a power of 90%. Age (years), Prostate Volume (ml), Resected tissue (gms), Resection time (minutes), Pre-op HB (gm/dl), Post-op HB (gm/dl), Pre-op HCT (percent), Post-op HCT (percent) had been assessed in the two groups. A p-value of 0.05 was considered significant.

Variable descriptive analyses were provided as frequencies and percentages. For normally distributed continuous data, mean and standard deviation was calculated, whereas, for skewed continuous variables, the median with interquartile range (IQR) was computed. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to determine the data's normality, with a significant difference value of $p = 0.05$. The t-test was used for regularly distributed continuous data and the Kruskal-Wallis test was used for asymmetric continuous variables to see if there was a difference between the two groups. The Chi-square test was used to find a connection between two categorical variables with a significance threshold of 0.05. (p value). IBM SPSS (Statistical Packages of Social Sciences) version 20 was used to analyses all of the data.

Results

A total of 40 patients were included in this randomized controlled trial, with equal number of patients in each group.

The demographical characteristics of both study groups were analyzed and are shown in **Table 1**. Mean Age of patients in Group A and Group B was 66.30 ± 9.24 years and 65.65 ± 7.43 respectively, with no significant difference between both groups ($p=0.808$). Median and IQR Prostatic volume in Group A and Group B was 68.0, 15, and 64.0, 21 respectively, with no significant difference between both groups ($p=0.372$).

The laboratory parameters were also quantified and compared and are shown in **Table 2**. Mean \pm S.D Pre-op HB of patients in Group A and Group B was 13.08 ± 0.66 and 12.69 ± 1.03 respectively, with no significant difference between both groups ($p=0.173$). Mean \pm S.D Post-op HB of patients in Group A and Group B was 11.93 ± 0.62 and 10.87 ± 1.54 respectively, with significant difference between both groups ($p=0.007$). Mean \pm S.D Loss of HB of patients in Group A and Group B was 1.15 ± 0.42 and 1.87 ± 1.04 respectively, with significant difference between both groups ($p=0.007$). Mean \pm S.D Pre-op HCT of patients in Group A and Group B was 41.63 ± 3.54 and 39.25 ± 4.02 respectively, with no significant difference between both groups ($p=0.054$). Mean \pm S.D Post-op HCT of patients in Group A and Group B was 38.47 ± 3.50 and 34.44 ± 4.34 respectively, with significant difference between both groups ($p=0.003$). Mean \pm S.D Loss of HCT of patients in Group A and Group B was 3.16 ± 1.50 and 4.81 ± 2.79 respectively, with significant difference between both groups ($p=0.026$). Median and IQR Resected tissue of patients in Group A and Group B was 41.0, 18 and 30.0, 12 respectively, with significant difference between both groups ($p=0.017$). Median and IQR Irrigation fluid of patients in Group A and Group B was 18.50 , 6 and 25.0 , 10 respectively, with highly significant difference between both groups ($p=0.001$) [**Table-2**]. Blood transfusion was not observed in any patients of Group A while 6 patients in Group B were transfused, showing significant difference between both groups ($p=0.001$) [**Table-2**].

Table 1 - BASELINE CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Variables	Groups		p Value
	TURP with Epinephrine n=120	TURP with Normal saline n=120	
Age (years) (mean with S.D)	66.30 ± 9.24	65.65 ± 7.43	0.808
Prostate size (gms) (median with IQR)	68.00 , 15	64.00 , 21	0.372

Table 2 – LABORATORY AND OPERATIVE PARAMETERS

Variables	Groups		p Value
	TURP with Epinephrine n=120	TURP with Normal saline n=120	
Pre-op HB (mg/dL) (mean with S.D)	13.08 ± 0.66	12.69 ± 1.03	0.173
Post-op HB (mg/dL) (mean with S.D)	11.93 ± 0.62	10.87 ± 1.54	0.007
Loss of HB (mg/dL) (mean with S.D)	1.15 ± 0.42	1.87 ± 1.04	0.007
Pre-op HCT (%) (mean with S.D)	41.63 ± 3.54	39.25 ± 4.02	0.054
Post-op HCT (%) (mean with S.D)	38.47 ± 3.50	34.44 ± 4.34	0.003
Loss of HCT (%) (mean with S.D)	3.16 ± 1.50	4.81 ± 2.79	0.026
Resection Time (min) (median with IQR)	30.00 , 19	42.50 , 19	0.024
Resected Tissue (gms) (median with IQR)	41.00 , 18	30.00 , 12	0.017
Irrigation Fluid (litres) (median with IQR)	18.50 , 06	25.00 , 10	0.001

Blood Transfusion (n)	0	6	0.010
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Discussion

BPH is a common clinical condition in the elderly male population and affects their standard of living. Age, race, genetics, food, physical exercise, and comorbidities are all factors that influence it.⁹ It is caused by prostatic cell proliferation leading to obstructive urinary tract disease resulting in Lower Urinary Tract Symptoms (LUTS). BPH can be treated medically in the majority of the cases, using 5 alpha-reductase inhibitors. Various surgical procedures have also been developed to manage this disease when medical treatment fails.

Among the surgical options, Transurethral Resection of Prostate (TURP) continues to be the most common procedure. It is an elective treatment that improves LUTS and eliminates the need for lifelong catheterization in patients all over the world, including the old and fragile.¹⁰ The most common complications associated with this surgery include the inability to urinate (6%), surgical revision (5.6%), substantial UTI (3.6%), Transurethral resection Syndrome (1.5%) and intraoperative or postoperative blood loss requiring blood transfusions (3%).¹¹

To minimize the blood loss, alpha-blockers and 5 α inhibitors (5-ARIs) have been used as the primary treatment for large-sized prostates before surgery. The major purpose of these drugs is to lower the level of active testosterone, dihydrotestosterone (DHT), minimizing the blood loss by reducing the prostate size.^{12,13,14}

A study published in the East Central African journal in 2013, collected data of 228 patients, 128 of whom had undergone TURP. They found that the transfusion incidence in these patients was 58.2% and a total whole blood transfusion rate was 1.2 units per case. They discovered that with careful planning, proper transfusion protocols, and surgical expertise, along with the use of intraprostatic epinephrine injections, this high incidence of blood transfusions in TURP patients can be brought down.¹⁵

Many agents have been used in the past to achieve hemostasis to reduce blood loss during the Transurethral resection of prostate. M. Luke et al. tested BERIPLAST (fibrin sealant) as a local injecting agent during TURP in Sundby Hospital, Denmark, in the hopes of minimizing postoperative blood loss. According to the findings, patients who were treated with fibrin glue in the prostatic cavity had much less post-operative bleeding, ($p < 0.01$).¹⁶ Later in 2016, Mohammad Hatef Khorrani et al. had a similar concept and retested the same idea, utilizing fibrin glue injections in the prostatic fossa and saw a tremendous response in TURP patients in terms of reduced blood loss, corroborating the idea that fibrin decreases blood loss post-surgery.¹⁷

Use of tranexamic acid (TXA) to minimize blood loss in patients undergoing total hip arthroplasty (THA) or total knee arthroplasty (TKA) is well accepted.¹⁸ It is commonly used as a potent and reliable drug for decreasing bleeding and transfusion rates, in cardiac, orthopaedic, gynecological, transplant surgeries, and urological procedures, especially TURP.¹⁹ A small number of authors asserted that TXA has a dose-dependent effect when administered during B-TURP and found that high-dose TXA significantly reduced the drop-in hemoglobin and ultimately need of blood transfusions when compared to placebo.²⁰ However, new research is now bringing to light the promising benefits of epinephrine in lowering blood loss in patients, particularly those undergoing total joint arthroplasty (TJA)^{21,22}. This, in effect, reduces the need for post-operative transfusions^{23,24}.

Epinephrine, is a hormone, a medicine, and a well-known vasoconstrictor widely used in different parts of the body, especially the smooth muscles, leading to a decrease in blood flow. A trial was conducted by *Sonny Schelin* in Kalmar County Hospital, Sweden, in 2009 in which the prostate gland was injected with Mepivacaine epinephrine (Carbocain-Adrenalin®) before surgery, and different prostate surgery techniques were compared in terms of their pros and cons. He utilized the idea of using Mepivacaine epinephrine and found fruitful results regarding blood loss and resection time as there was excellent visibility and less time consumption for coagulating vessels intraoperatively, saving patients from morbidity and cost of additional procedures.²⁵

Pre-operatively for tonsillectomy, levobupivacaine, a solitary S-enantiomer of bupivacaine, was employed as a novel amide local anesthetic that resulted in a considerable reduction in intraoperative blood loss.²⁶ Epinephrine with lidocaine was also experimented with different concentrations (1:50,000, 1:200,000 and 1:100,000) and surgeons found excellent success in lowering perioperative bleeding with 1:50,000, while comparing to 1:20,000 and no significant difference found when compared 1:200,000 with 1:100,000.²⁷

In our study, Patients in our Case group A, who received intraprostatic epinephrine injection during TURP, before tissue resection was performed, had a significantly lower blood loss than those in the Control Group B, who received normal saline. This comparison was made by measuring and comparing the pre-operative as well as post-operative Hemoglobin and Hematocrit levels of patients in both groups. In effect, the patients in Group A did not require any blood transfusion whereas 6 of the patients in Group B underwent transfusion of blood.

Another important factor to note was the fact that it was possible to remove a greater amount of tissue in patients belonging to Group A, as a result of lower level of bleeding, better visibility and lesser time spent in achieving hemostasis. The decrease in peroperative bleeding also led to lesser irrigation fluid being used in Group A, compared to Group B with shorter, overall, procedure time.

Conclusion

To conclude, our study was able to demonstrate that the use of Intraprostatic Epinephrine injection in TURP led to significantly lesser blood loss, larger amount of tissue to be resected, lesser operative time and decreased need for blood transfusion.

Conflict Of Interest

None to declare.

Disclosure

Not part of any dissertation or thesis.

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Patient Consent

Well informed consent in English and Urdu (native language) was taken from all patients of the study.

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References

- Bipolar TURP in the treatment of bladder outflow obstruction by GM Pirola-2021— Published 9 July 2021
Volume 2021:13 Pages 487—494. DOI ... Giacomo Maria Pirola,1 Martina Maggi,2 Daniele Castellani,3 Alessandro Sciarra,2
- Wu DB-C, Yee CH, Ng C-F, Lee SWH, Chaiyakunapruk N, Chang Y-S, et al. Economic evaluation of combination therapy versus monotherapy for treatment of benign prostatic hyperplasia in Hong Kong. *Front Pharmacol* [Internet]. 2018;9:1078. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2018>.
- Hollingsworth JM, Wei JT. Economic impact of surgical intervention in the treatment of benign prostatic hyperplasia. *Rev Urol* [Internet]. 2006 [cited 2022 Feb 6];8 Suppl 3(Suppl3):S9–15. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/labs/pmc/articles/PMC1686802/>
- Fusco F, Creta M, Trama F, Esposito F, Crocetto F, Aveta A, Mangiapia F, Imbimbo C, Capece M, La Rocca R, Mirone V. Tamsulosin plus a new complementary and alternative medicine in patients with lower urinary tract symptoms suggestive of benign prostatic hyperplasia: Results from a retrospective comparative study. *Archivio Italiano di Urologia e Andrologia*. 2020 Oct 1;92(3).
- Talic RF, Al Rikabi AC. Transurethral Vaporization–Resection of the Prostate versus Standard Transurethral Prostatectomy: Comparative Changes in Histopathological Features of the Resected Specimens. *European urology*. 2000;37(3):301-5.
- Peng B, Huang J, Wang G, Zhang H, Liu M. Transurethral enucleation of prostate with button electrode plasmakinetic vaporization for the treatment of Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia. *Scientific reports*. 2016 Dec 23;6(1):1-4.
- Qian X, Liu H, Xu D, Xu L, Huang F, He W, Qi J, Zhu Y, Xu D. Functional outcomes and complications following B-TURP versus HoLEP for the treatment of benign prostatic hyperplasia: a review of the literature and Meta-analysis. *The Aging Male*. 2017 Jul 3;20(3):184-91.
- Marszalek M, Ponholzer A, Pusman M, Berger I, Madersbacher S. Transurethral resection of the prostate. *European urology supplements*. 2009 Apr 1;8(6):504-12.
- Lim KB. Epidemiology of clinical benign prostatic hyperplasia. *Asian journal of urology*. 2017 Jul 1;4(3):148-51.

- Suskind AM, Walter LC, Zhao S, Finlayson E. Functional outcomes after transurethral resection of the prostate in nursing home residents. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*. 2017 Apr;65(4):699-703.
- Reich O, Gratzke C, Bachmann A, Seitz M, Schlenker B, Hermanek P, et al. Morbidity, mortality and early outcome of transurethral resection of the prostate: a prospective multicenter evaluation of 10,654 patients. *J Urol* [Internet]. 2008;180(1):246–9. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022534708006186>
- Kim KS, Jeong WS, Park SY, Kim YT, Moon HS. The effect of two weeks of treatment with dutasteride on bleeding after transurethral resection of the prostate. *The world journal of men's health*. 2015 Apr 1;33(1):14-9.
- Bansal A, Arora A. Transurethral resection of prostate and bleeding: a prospective, randomized, double-blind placebo-controlled trial to see the efficacy of short-term use of finasteride and dutasteride on operative blood loss and prostatic microvessel density. *Journal of endourology*. 2017 Sep 1;31(9):910-7.
- Kloping Y, Yogiswara N, Azmi Y. The role of preoperative dutasteride in reducing bleeding during transurethral resection of the prostate: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Asian Journal of Urology*. 2021 Jun 8.
- Mteta KA, Musau P, Keiza N. Blood Transfusion in Transurethral Resection of the Prostate (TURP): A Practice that Can be Avoided. *East and Central African Journal of Surgery*. 2012;17(2):102-5.
- Luke M, Kvist E, Andersen F, Hjortrup A. Reduction of post-operative bleeding after transurethral resection of the prostate by local instillation of fibrin adhesive (Beriplast). *British journal of urology*. 1986 Dec;58(6):672-5.
- Khorrani MH, Tadaion F, Ghanaat I, Alizadeh F. The efficacy of fibrin glue injection in the prostatic fossa on decreasing postoperative bleeding following transurethral resection of prostate. *Advanced biomedical research*. 2016;5.
- Meng QQ, Pan N, Xiong JY, Liu N. Tranexamic acid is beneficial for reducing perioperative blood loss in transurethral resection of the prostate. *Experimental and therapeutic medicine*. 2019 Jan 1;17(1):943-7.
- Gupta A, Priyadarshi S, Vyas N, Sharma G. Efficacy of tranexamic acid in decreasing primary hemorrhage in transurethral resection of the prostate: A novel combination of intravenous and topical approach. *Urology Annals*. 2021 Jul;13(3):238
- Samir M, Saafan AM, Afifi RM, Tawfick A. Can high-dose tranexamic acid have a role during transurethral resection of the prostate in large prostates? A randomised controlled trial. *Arab Journal of Urology*. 2021 Jun 4:1-6.
- Liu H, Liu Z, Zhang Q, Guo W. Utilization of epinephrine-soaked gauzes to address bleeding from osteotomy sites in non-tourniquet total knee arthroplasty: a retrospective cohort study. *BMC Musculoskeletal Disorders*. 2020 Dec;21(1):1-8.
- Teng Y, Ma J, Ma X, Wang Y, Lu B, Guo C. The efficacy and safety of epinephrine for postoperative bleeding in total joint arthroplasty: A PRISMA-compliant meta-analysis. *Medicine*. 2017 Apr;96(17).
- Menon S (1008) Epinephrine Preinjection of stalked colonic polyps. *Gastrointest Endosc* 67 (7):1214
- Lira-Dale A, Maldonado-Avila M, Gil-García JF, Mues-Guizar EH, Nerubay-Toiber R, Guzmán-Esquivel J, Delgado-Enciso I. Effect of intraprostatic epinephrine on intraoperative blood loss reduction during transurethral resection of the prostate. *International urology and nephrology*. 2012 Apr;44(2):365-9.
- Schelin S. Transurethral resection of the prostate after intraprostatic injections of mepivacain epinephrine: a preliminary communication. *Scandinavian journal of urology and nephrology*. 2009 Jan 1;43(1):63-7.
- Tas E, Hanci V, Ugur MB, Turan IO, Yigit VB, Cinar F. Does preincisional injection of levobupivacaine with epinephrine have any benefits for children undergoing tonsillectomy? An intraindividual evaluation. *International journal of pediatric otorhinolaryngology*. 2010 Oct 1;74(10):1171-5.
- Shoroghi M, Sadrolsadat SH, Razzaghi M, Farahbakhsh F, Sheikhvatan M, Sheikhfathollahi M, et al. Effect of different epinephrine concentrations on local bleeding and hemodynamics during dermatologic surgery. *Acta Dermatovenerol Croat* [Internet]. 2008 [cited 2022 Feb 8];16(4):209–14. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19111145/>

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